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Developing wage payment system in a production company by applying time study and work evaluation techniques

Hasanov Parviz¹, Najimbayli Khazar²

¹ Assoc. Prof. at the Industrial Engineering Department;
Baku Engineering University; Republic of Azerbaijan

² Master, Lecturer at the Industrial Engineering Department;
Baku Engineering University; Republic of Azerbaijan

Abstract. In any production system one the main costs are wage paid to the workers. The wage payment system is not only influencing the overall costs, the system also is related to the productivity in the production system directly. The right wage payment system is so important to manage the workers efficiently, to motivate the workers with right incentive payment system, to figure out nonvalue-added activities by investigation on work tasks and etc. In most of the production companies the wage payments are based on time the workers spend for the tasks. This technique can be accepted as one of the best techniques. By this kind of wage payment system, the company assures that they will get benefit by paying salary to the workers. By careful observations and time-keeping techniques this kind of wage payment system can be converted from time base to unit product base. For developing wage payment system in the unit product base, the companies must determine the time required to produce any product accurately. After this for every kind task time tolerances must be arranged. Finally, standard time can be accepted and applied in the production. This paper emphasizes some main techniques on standard time calculation.

Keywords: *work evaluation, normal time, standard time, wage payment system, stopwatch technique.*

Nomenclature

In investigation of a production system, the time the workers spend to any task is the main point to give the right decisions about the system. For this we need to create time standards by observations and time measurement.

In time measurement technique the main idea is to find standard time for any work or task. Stopwatch technique is the one of the most important techniques in this process. By the stopwatch technique we need to calculate the average time for any task. *The average time* is calculated by eliminating abnormal time measures to increase accuracy. After this we

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need to find normal time:

$$\text{Average time} * \frac{\text{rating}}{100} = \text{normal time}$$

Rating = Technologist's opinion on the operator's performance

Normal time = Indicates the time for a normal operator to perform any task

The normal time cannot be accepted as standard time for any task. Because in any work the tolerance is so important to provide the accuracy in time measurement. By considering the allowance to stop in any task the calculated time standard will be the guaranteed measurement:

$$\text{Normal time} + \text{allowances} = \text{standard time}$$

After determining the standard time, we can evaluate the work of any worker. The rating can be calculated by this equation:

$$\frac{\text{Standard time}}{\text{actual time}} = \text{actual rating}$$

The actual rating can be accepted as the performance of the operator.

Introduction

At the beginning we can say that the wage payment systems are related to many factors for any company. Actually, the time required for the tasks is so important in this system, but the secondary factors cannot be ignored. Work conditions, like risk factor, ergonomic conditions, harmful results of the job and etc. factors, are influencing the wage payment system directly. Researcher Kyung Yong Rhee, Young Sun Kim, Yoon Ho Cho emphasized the work conditions very carefully and its impact on the payment system [1]. The observations indicate that not only the ergonomic and other kind of conditions must be considered in the payment systems, also they must be improved to get more efficient production system. At the result, we can say that one of the biggest advantages of work investigation is the development of work conditions.

Additionally, we can add that one of the main factors in the wage payment systems is considering the minimum and

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average wage level in the following labor market. The report of International Labor Office indicates some main points according to the topic [2].

Content

This paper indicates the importance of work investigation and time study. Time study is a part of work study techniques. The calculations and measurements on any task investigated in this technique. Time study is so important to assign time standards for any task. For this we need to calculate normal time, consider the time allowances for delaying and work rate of every worker, decide standard time at the end. After carefully applying these steps, we can be sure that the calculations are accurate and precise as we need.

As indicated above to get correct time standards for any task we need to keep the time required for the task very carefully. However, it not the new technique, the most efficient technique in this procedure is stopwatch techniques. Before giving the right decisions on wage payment systems, we need to be sure that the time calculations are accurate. Stopwatch technique demands just observation and keeping time for any activity. Especially, we can say that in any production system the activities can be categorized into 5 groups (operation, inspection, transportation, storage, delay). The behavior to these types of activities really depends on characteristics of activities. By time study we can improve the production systems by improving operations, managing inspections efficiently, organizing transportations safely and efficiently, managing the storing process, eliminating the delays as possible as we can [3].

Collecting data by stopwatch technique

As mentioned above, the most famous technique in time study is stopwatch technique. Here, we need to be careful on the analysis of data collected. In the analysis the unusual data must be ignored, the average value must be considered. In the stopwatch technique the records usually are done in second base. However, 60 seconds is accepted as one minute, in analysis the time units will be accepted as second.

One of the main factors in time study is to accept the rating for any operator correctly. The rating will be influenced by 4 factors: skill, consistency, working conditions, effort (this factor is the most important one and influences the others as well) [3].

The allowances are also main factor in time study, especially in stopwatch technique. It must be indicated that the allowance cannot be accepted as fixed percentage for any kind of tasks. According to the characteristics of task the

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allowance percentages can be accepted differently.

Application stopwatch technique in a production company

In the production company we investigating the wage payment system is not developed in time base. The company was calculating the wages by considering the selling prices of any product. The wages are accepted as some fixed percentages of selling prices, so this calculation guarantees that the wages will not bring out any lose at the end. But this additionally brings injustice to the production system. Because in some products some production processes can require additional time and effort, and the selling price for the product can be less than the other products. In this case, the wage payment systems must base to observations and correct investigation. Additionally in this kind of production systems that the wages are calculated as percentages of selling prices, the production capacities cannot be figured out correctly. In this case, the company is just producing the products and is not interested to investigate the problem, delay, undesired results and etc. We can say that in this kind of wage payment system, the management cannot focus to the processes in any production system. They generally focus on results. This means that the possible wastes inside the production process can be skipped in this technique.

After the initial observations, we kept time by stopwatch technique. In the observation the rating for a worker was not known. That is why, the data for the process is collected by observing 3 different workers that the result can be accepted as the final average data by this method.

In this process, the 61st data is unusual data for the process. After ignoring the 61st number, the average time is calculated and the process takes approximately 2.76 seconds. This process is done manually and in manual processes, especially in the processes takes a little time, the allowances must be considered carefully. In automatic processes the amplitude between the biggest and smallest values probably will not be observed in high value. But for manual processes this tendency changes. The human factors always influence the processes and delays occurs. That is why we accepted 50% idle time for the following production process. At the end the standard time for the task is calculated as 5.52 seconds. This kind of time keeping and calculations is done for approximately all the production processes. Only for the processes that the average time can be estimated similar to the other processes the calculations are simplified.

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Table 1

Stamping process time durations. Stopwatch technique

Cutting metal from the metal list process (after forming) (a totally of 78 observations are done)														
№	Lap (sec)	Sum (sec)	№	Lap (sec)	Sum (sec)	№	Lap (sec)	Sum (sec)	№	Lap (sec)	Sum (sec)	№	Lap (sec)	Sum (sec)
1	2,70	2,70	17	2,30	47,72	33	2,50	91,91	49	2,27	134,35	65	2,65	276,38
2	3,48	6,18	18	2,54	50,26	34	2,54	94,45	50	2,45	136,80	66	3,16	279,54
3	2,32	8,50	19	2,61	52,87	35	2,51	96,96	51	3,32	140,12	67	1,85	281,39
4	2,88	11,38	20	4,42	57,29	36	2,92	99,88	52	2,92	143,04	68	2,94	284,33
5	2,69	14,07	21	2,95	60,24	37	2,89	102,77	53	3,41	146,45	69	3,22	287,55
6	2,48	16,55	22	2,28	62,52	38	3,67	106,44	54	2,15	148,60	70	3,28	290,83
7	3,08	19,63	23	2,17	64,69	39	2,94	109,38	55	2,22	150,82	71	2,43	293,26
8	2,64	22,27	24	2,85	67,54	40	3,22	112,60	56	2,52	153,34	72	3,04	296,30
9	3,85	26,12	25	2,52	70,06	41	2,32	114,92	57	3,02	156,36	73	2,71	299,01
10	1,42	27,54	26	2,63	72,69	42	2,06	116,98	58	2,36	158,72	74	2,70	301,71
11	2,43	29,97	27	2,60	75,29	43	2,37	119,35	59	3,02	161,74	75	2,80	304,51
12	4,27	34,24	28	2,72	78,01	44	2,57	121,92	60	2,95	164,69	76	2,52	307,03
13	2,72	36,96	29	2,73	80,74	45	2,15	124,07	61	101,12	265,81	77	2,98	310,01
14	2,18	39,14	30	3,39	84,13	46	2,61	126,68	62	3,15	268,96	78	3,25	313,26
15	3,00	42,14	31	2,78	86,91	47	3,07	129,75	63	2,42	271,38			
16	3,28	45,42	32	2,50	89,41	48	2,33	132,08	64	2,35	273,73			
Average = 2.76 seconds / 50% idle time considered / 5.52 seconds standard time accepted														

Conclusion

For every process the time study, especially stopwatch technique, applied and by considering the time required to perform any task, the wage payment systems updated according to these calculations. For deciding the wage for every task correctly the labor market investigation and determination of average salary decided in any similar work are so important. We accepted the average salary for polishing processes as 600 dollars, and stamping and painting processes as 1060 dollars by considering the labor market. After this, the salary in some of the processes are decided like given in the table below:

Table 2

Wage arranged per unit product by production processes. For every process the salary is calculated

Part 1 stamping processes	Day/1000 units	Daily capacity (units)	Daily salary (AZN)	Salary per unit (AZN)
Part 1 stamping	0.14	7200	81.82	0.0114
Part 1 bending	0.20	4950	81.82	0.0165
Total	0.34	2933	81.82	0.0279
Part 2 stamping processes	Day/1000 units	Daily capacity (units)	Daily salary (AZN)	Salary per unit (AZN)

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Table continuation 2

Part 2 cutting from metal list	0.13	7819	81.82	0.0105
Part 2 forming process	0.86	1158**	81.82	0.0706
Part 2 cutting borders accurately	0.39	2543***	81.82	0.0322
Total	1.38	722	81.82	0.1133
Part 3 stamping processes	Day/1000 units	Daily capacity (units)	Daily salary (AZN)	Salary per unit (AZN)
Part 3 cutting from metal list	0.14	7200	81.82	0.0114
Part 3 forming process	0.78	1280	81.82	0.0639
Part 3 cutting borders accurately	0.19	5227*	81.82	0.0157
Total	1.11	900	81.82	0.0909
Part 4 stamping processes	Day/1000 units	Daily capacity (units)	Daily salary (AZN)	Salary per unit (AZN)
Part 4 cutting from metal list	0.12	8553	81.82	0.0096
Part 4 forming process	0.47	2116	81.82	0.0387
Part 4 cutting borders accurately	0.18	5622	81.82	0.0146
Total	0.77	1303	81.82	0.0628
The additional part stamping process	Day/1000 units	Daily capacity (units)	Daily salary (AZN)	Salary per unit (AZN)
Additional part	0.14	7200	81.82	0.0114
Stamping processes total time	3.74	Final wage per unit product:		0.6014

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